

On a Gender Lens and Democratic Backsliding

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How does a gender lens help us understand or explain democratic backsliding? It does so in several ways, but not exclusively. Class also plays a significant role, as it intertwines with gender revealing the structural forces behind both democratic backsliding and the rise of right-wing populism. In this regard, I offer four points for reflection.

First, we have come to understand gender as a social relationship of inequality (historically between women and men, but now understood to include a broader spectrum of gender identities) that influences access to economic and political power. Historically, political power has been dominated by men, who distribute political and economic resources among loyalists in the broad male population. This has been the case in democracies as well, at least until relatively recently in modern history, when first-wave feminist movements fought for women's suffrage and later for parliamentary quotas to increase women's political representation. Such quotas had earlier been established in Bolshevik Russia and later spread across Communist states.

Second, the social relations of gender have always been mediated by class. It is rare to find working-class representatives in positions of power, especially since the onset of the neo-

liberal model of capitalism in the late 20th century and the weakening of trade unions. In the USA in particular, the pursuit of political office relies on raising vast amounts of money, much of which comes from donors within the capitalist class. It is no accident that more such funding goes to male candidates than to female candidates, which is why the U.S. has considerably less women's parliamentary representation than elsewhere, whether compared to its peers in the Global North or many countries in the Global South. As of July 2024, the US is ranked 72 for women's parliamentary representation by the Interparliamentary Union, below Vietnam, Cuba, and Armenia and most Western democracies.

Third, we have come to expect that gender matters in domestic and international politics. Feminist scholarship has analyzed the ways in which certain forms of "hegemonic masculinity" are implicated in authoritarianism and militarism, especially in the absence of robust women's political representation. Yet, despite increases in women's political power, recent years have seen a rise in right-wing populism, authoritarian politics, and increases in military spending—all occurring in what were supposed to be strong democracies. US democracy has always been flawed, but its decades-long reliance on high military

spending and vast arms sales to “partners and allies” contribute to a fraught international environment and heightened democratic backsliding. In the Global South, India is a case in point, with its turn toward Hindu chauvinism.

Israel’s democracy has long been backsliding due to various governments’ inability or unwillingness to play a more constructive and peaceful regional role or to adequately integrate its Arab (Christian and Muslim) citizenry. In the past, Israeli feminists embarked on a very promising National Action Plan for implementation of the UN’s Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace, and Security, but had to abandon the project (Moghadam 2023). The Jewish chauvinism of the Netanyahu regime has accelerated democratic backsliding. In Turkey, a central aspect of democratic backsliding has been the instrumentalization of women’s rights to mobilize conservative women in support of the ruling party’s increasingly authoritarian and patriarchal agenda (Arat 2022). Religious/ethnic/national chauvinism and militarism are gendered phenomena, reflective of egregious hyper-masculinity and destructive of the promises of democracy and equality, not to mention regional and world peace.

Fourth, it appears that the women in positions of political power neither prevent nor stop democratic backsliding, and some contribute to it as leaders of right-wing populist parties (Moghadam and Kaftan 2019; *The Economist* 2023). Outside of the Middle East, Argentina, Nicaragua, and Ethiopia have very high percentages of women’s parliamentary representation, yet they all have experienced democratic backsliding—and in Ethiopia’s case, a tragic civil conflict. Argentina’s new president is almost belligerent in his embrace of neoliberal capitalism, which will doubtless-

ly come at the expense of low-income women and men.

What appears to matter is not so much the numbers or percentages of women in political power, but their capacity to mobilize support—in political society as well as in civil society—for a robust social democracy. Where we might find such mobilizations is a key question for research. ♦

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